

Taming Doubts - How to semantically model fuzzy and wobbly georeferences in archaeology and in the geosciences

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1 Introduction

Data modelling in archaeological research must handle uncertainty and ambiguities, especially in georeferencing. This enables re-using research data using the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Open Science while guaranteeing data quality. Furthermore, for linking data, modelling vagueness, georeferencing methods and events, and FAIRification, graph-based modelling as Linked Open Data (LOD) proposed by Berners-Lee is the method and technique of choice. However, due to the enormous variety of research domains, an interdisciplinary, commonly understandable modelling of uncertainties and vagueness in research data is highly challenging. We will present two data-driven interdisciplinary use cases for dealing with and modelling vague and uncertain georeferenced findspots as LOD from the archaeological and geosciences domains.

Graph-based data modelling uses three technologies: (I) Wikidata, (II) ontologies and Linked Open data using the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (FSLO), and (III) Wikibase. The main modelling idea is to publish and model the following georeferencing information as Linked Open Data: (1) describe where the geoinformation comes from, (2) describe the method of how the coordinate was created, (3) describe the uncertainty issue(s), and (4) use references into the Semantic Web.

Methods I-III can be applied to at least use cases from the archaeological and geosciences domain: Ogham Stones in Ireland and the Eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite.

2 Modelling Strategies

2.1 Wikidata

The geographical location of sites and archaeological artefacts can be described in Wikidata using coordinates (P625). These coordinates contain uncertainty and reference information that can be modelled using Wikidata qualifiers and reference boundaries. In the case of Ogham stones inspected during on-site surveys, this can be done as follows:

- qualifier: sourcing circumstances (P1180), stated in (P248), location (P276), determination method (P459), subject has role (P2868)
- reference: OpenStreetMap node ID (P11693)

Locations / artefacts that are only accessible in the literature / online databases receive the following modelling:

- qualifier: stated in (P248), object has role (P3831), determination method (P459), subject has role (P2868)
- reference: reference URL (P854)

2.2 Wikibase

Wikibase modelling is related to the Wikidata modelling approach. Here, a location also has a latitude/longitude coordinate, which is provided with a qualifier to further describe it with the following attributes: has certainty level, certainty description, method used, acting person, has source, has source subtype, method description.

2.3 Linked Open Data

The Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (fsl) is based on PROV-O, SKOS and GeoSPARQL.

It follows the PROV-O concept of entity, activity and agent. In the case of this ontology, sites (entities) have a geometry and were created with a method (activity) by a person (agent), cf. **Fig. 1**.

Site and geometry contain two properties for describing fuzziness: `fsl:certaintyDesc` and `fsl:certaintyLevel`; sites additionally receive properties for describing references, e.g. for books, `fsl:hasReference` or to online resources, e.g. via exact-match properties from the SKOS vocabulary.

Fig 1. Scheme of the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

3 Use Case Wikidata: Irish Ogham Stones

Ogham stones are monoliths bearing inscriptions in the early medieval Gaelic "primitive Irish" Ogham script, which were erected mainly on the island of Ireland and in the western part of Great Britain between the 4th and 9th centuries AD. Most of the stones are no longer in their original location, which is important for cartographic recording and makes it difficult to determine their original function. Ogham stone finds are treated in various analogue catalogues such as books, online databases (e.g. the CISP project) or online repositories (e.g. Ogham in 3D). These sources provide information at different levels of granularity: townlands, descriptions and coordinates in WGS84/GPS or Irish GRID references. In addition, entire biographies of geo-locations are recorded there. One example of this is CIIC 81, which is exhibited in the Stone Corridor of University College Cork (UCC) and was also modelled with OpenStreetMap, see OSM Node 11071361392. The entry for the Ogham stone CIIC 81 in the Thesaurus of Indo-European Text and Language Materials (TITUS) by Prof. Jost Gippert shows, and Ó Ríordáin (1931) continues as shown below. This courtyard is also shown in plans by Ó Ríordáin & Ryan, which can still be georeferenced (**Fig. 2**).

TITUS: "According to Brash [...] the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheennagreine, in the townland of Gurranes [...] Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurranes. [...] The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17."; Ó Ríordáin (1931): "This lios [Lisheennagreine, the little fort of the sun] has been levelled but the sign of its position may be seen in the field (in Kelly's farm). In this lios was discovered the large Ogham stone now in University College, Cork. The stone was discovered by a farmer while eating potatoes on the site of the lios [...] and was then placed in a neighbouring fence [...] and] removed to University College."

4 Use Case Linked Open Data: Campanian Ignimbrite

About 40,000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields. Evidence of the ash fall from this late Pleistocene volcanic event, which originated in the Campania region (Italy), can be found throughout Central Europe. After the eruption, massive glass deposits covered large parts of the Eastern European continent; volcanic material from the CI is often found in isolated watersheds and valleys. These sites are recorded in several publications, e.g. by precise coordinates or references to cities, regions, caves and archaeological sites. The georeferencing of the Urluia site (URL) in Romania is difficult. The literature provides the following clues:

Fitzsimmons & Hambach (2014), p.76 wrote: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities." Pötter et al. (2021), p.5 added: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obrecht et al., 2017)."

The location coordinate POINT(18.4815 42.7790) can be approximately determined from both pieces of information. Information from OpenStreetMap helps here (**Fig. 3**).

Fig 2. Left: Plan showing the location of (A) Lisnacaheragh Ringfort and (H) Lisheennagreine; centre: present-day OSM map; right: description of Ogham Stone CIIC 81 in the UCC Stone Corridor.

Fig 3. Aerial line measurement between the possible location (URL) and the Danube; right: map showing the opencast mine and the possible URL coordinate POINT(18.4815 42.7790).